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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project continuous and currently ongoing communication activities on different social platforms.

All partners are responsible of this key deliverable; The social accounts used by the project are the PPs' social accounts (mainly facebook and twitter) as well as GUTTA LinkedIn and ResearchGate accounts.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at <https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>.

2. Introduction

Social media are becoming more and more important to reach a wide range of target audiences. They are crucial even for the communication and dissemination activities of publicly funded projects. GUTTA project developed its online presence through some social media channels fitting with its communication objectives and being in line with the specificities of its target audiences.

Social media are very diverse, need regular feeds and their full exploitation and use can be time consuming, but have the advantage of being a two-way communication channels, enabling the project management to get useful feedback from the project target groups.

For GUTTA, they include:

- Under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia
- General public (i.e. passengers, consumers)

During the IT-HR Programme kick-off meeting (Nov. 2016) Agnes Monfret of DG REGIO (Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy) discussed statistical data indicating that Under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia have a scarce awareness of EU-funded CB programmes. GUTTA targeted also this group, aiming at raising the awareness of the beneficial effect of the EU cohesion policy especially using social media networks, considered as crucial to reach general public and this specific target group.

3. Social media activities

The following table illustrates the social accounts used by the project:

PPs	Social	Account name	Username	Url
all	ResearchGate	GUTTA - savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region		https://www.researchgate.net/project/GUTTA-savinG-fUel-and-emissions-from-mariTime-Transport-in-the-Adriatic-region
	LinkedIn	Italy-Croatia GUTTA project		https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12226084/
CMCC	Facebook	CMCC Climate	@CmccClimate	https://www.facebook.com/CmccClimate
	Twitter	CMCC Foundation VISIR	@CmccClimate @VISIRnavi	https://twitter.com/CmccClimate https://twitter.com/VISIRnavi
	You Tube	CMCC Channel		https://www.youtube.com/user/CMCCvideo
	LinkedIn	CMCC Foundation – Centro Euro-		https://www.linkedin.com/company/cmcc---centro-euro-

		Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici		mediterraneo-sui-cambiamenti-climatici/
	Instagram	Fondazione CMCC	cmccclimate	https://www.instagram.com/cmccclimate/
CSA	Facebook	CSA Mare Nostrum	@csamarenostrom	https://www.facebook.com/csamarenostrom/
UniZd	Facebook			https://www.facebook.com/unizd/

The project partners used, developed and animated the LinkedIn page “[Interreg Italy-Croatia GUTTA project](#)” and the Research Gate page “[GUTTA-savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region](#)” accounts.

Project partners’ social accounts (e.g. Facebook and Twitter) were also used to spread updates from the project. The aim was to inform and engage with stakeholders and the media. The networking activity on social media tried to target specific categories of stakeholders in order to collect information useful for the project database while enlarging the network by involving new interested parties.

Twitter activities was fast and interactive, thanks to the incorporation of hashtags and they targeted all stakeholders. LinkedIn was more corporate-oriented, with a slower pace in the publication and targeting professionals and other organisations involved in the maritime sector. Facebook was suitable for visual storytelling (e.g. photos and infographics) and they targeted in particular the general public and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia. Some hashtags were used, for example #maritime #transport #ferries #minimizeCO2 #GUTTA #Interreg #forecasts #ItalyCroatia.

Social platform updates were in English, Italian and Croatian.

The main inputs for GUTTA project activities on social media are PPs activities (e.g. participation to events, scientific deliverables such as publications, posters, conference papers). CMCC normally posted and/or re-launched contents created by each PP’s page or by the official social account of the Italy Croatia Interreg Programme (Twitter @ItalyCroatia).

The events listed in the shared calendar or communicated via regular e-mails or monthly skype meetings on communication activities represented the main source of information to cover events through social media.

Here some examples:

Fondazione Cmcc @CmccClimate · 18 de mar de 2019

Clean, #sustainable, #safe, and effective.
The #future of #maritime #transport in the #Adriatic Sea

#GUTTA (savinG fUel and #emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region) project just started.
@INTERREGTweets @interregeurope @gianandream

ow.ly/Fda850nqxzK

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VISIR 34 Tweet Following

VISIR @VISIRnavi · 3 ago

#VISIR ship routing model (using a graph-search method) compared to a @MIT model using PDEs: find the criterium for convergence and a case study in this month's issue of @IEEEorg Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems: bit.ly/34GzT7u

IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems

Name	Popular	Early Access	Current Issue
4-INV252	6,215	6,215	1,444

4-Inv252

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Gianandrea Mannarini added a research item Jul 1

EU-MRV: an analysis of 2018's Ro-Pax CO2 data

Conference Paper Jun 2020

Gianandrea Mannarini · Lorenzo Carelli · Amal Salhi

This paper analyses the EU-MRV dataset containing CO2 emission data from vessels calling at European harbours. The data is provided in an aggregated form for 2018 and we decided to focus on ferries...

Source

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VISIR @VISIRnavi · 9 ago 2019

June 14, 2019: Work with Lorenzo Carelli @CmccClimate and Dimitris Zisis et al. @MarineTraffic was awarded the best presentation award at the TransNav2019 conference (more than 100 papers presented!). Here the winning presentation: zenodo.org/record/3256112

1 3

VISIR 34 Tweet Following

VISIR ha ritwittato

Richard Meade @Lloydslisted · 21 feb

We have a climate emergency - we can't wait for the IMO, says Jutta Paulus, the European Parliament's emissions rapporteur. In this week's @LloydsList Podcast @Anastassios_LL meets her to discuss how to accelerate shipping decarbonisation

The Lloyd's List Podcast: Why the EU won't wait for IMO on climate c... We have a climate emergency, we can't wait for the IMO, claims Jutta Paulus, the European Parliament's maritime emissions rapporteur. Thi... lloydslist.maritimeintelligence.informa.com

1 10 14

Ocean Night #4 in Bari (14/12/2019)

GUTTA project 2nd SC Meeting (online event, 1-2 April 2020)

EUSEW2020 (22-26 June 2020)

The assessment of the project-internal CO2 emissions (D.1.2.6)

Posts:

Fondazione Cmcc @CmccClimate · 20 lug

How can we estimate the #CO2 #emissions related to a research project? How can we offset them? The @ItalyCroatia Interreg #GUTTAproject finds a way to successfully implement an EU project with zero net travel #emissions.

@gianandream @VISIRnavi
ow.ly/uLNU50ACzS6

CSA Mare Nostrum
27 maggio · 🌐

Kako procijeniti količinu CO2 emisija povezanih s istraživačkim projektima?
Odgovor možete pronaći u sljedećem članku u kojem je opisano kako GUTTA projekt doprinosi dekarbonizaciji prometa.

<https://www.cmcc.it/article/travelling-at-zero-net-co2-emissions-an-interreg-project-tells-how>

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CMCC.IT
Travelling at zero net CO2 emissions: an Interreg project

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Twitta

← #GUTTAproject

Popolari Recenti Persone Foto Video

Fondazione Cmcc @CmccClimate · 5 giu

We would like #GUTTAProject to be the first EU project with #zeronetCO2 #travels – @gianandream adds – and this can be done via negative emissions @ItalyCroatia
ow.ly/EiLE50zYTit

preparation phase | KOM SCm1

4. Conclusions

GUTTA project communication through social media has increased over time and is currently ongoing. In the future, the main effort will be to communicate using this media not only on the occasion of events or on the occasion of the release of deliverables, but also to engage and maintain regular conversation about maritime transport and cross-border initiatives with the main stakeholders and target groups of the project.

Following the recommendations of the SC meeting #2, the GUTTA partnership will continuously review information of the presence of all PPs on all social channels, in order to

amplify the messages from the GUTTA consortium. LP will collect these data from the PPs and will ensure that the communication flow is harmonized and coherent.

Furthermore, LP will ensure that the communication activities by individual PPs on this peculiar medium are aligned with both the IT-HR Interreg guidelines (Factsheet n. 81) and the GUTTA Communication Strategy (D. 2.1.3).

¹ https://www.italy-croatia.eu/documents/20126/87333/03-20180719_Factsheet_8_Communication.pdf/85ba26b6-9274-a11f-3ccd-1396be4f216d?t=1548328813954